

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE CONCEPT OF POSITIVITY AND ITS MANIFESTATION IN CHILDREN'S ACTIVITIES

S.Ashirova

Teacher of the Pedagogical Institute of Karshi State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818517>

Abstract. *The article discusses the meaning and definition of the word positive in science, its theoretical foundations, its place in Western philosophy, its manifestations and its importance in the activities of preschool children. - Comments on the importance of action and work, the information in the article is recommended for future professionals studying in the field of preschool education.*

Keywords: *positive, positivity, function, positivism, emotion, behavior, action, work.*

Introduction

The word positive is derived from the Latin word meaning "positive, positive" In the case of, which summarizes the ideas in the definitions given to this concept, we can define positivity as the reflection in the appearance of human feelings. The concepts of positivity and positivism appear in the form of as one of the main categories of philosophical science and begin to develop. Positivism is a very common trend in Western philosophy. It was founded by the French philosopher Auguste Comte in the 1930s.

- first, the true Anaganagaman moment against lies;
- secondly, usefulness against redundancy;
- third, the case against suspicion decimal;
- fourth, clarity against uncertainty, abstraction;
- fifthly, the positive against the negative
- Sixth, the salt against corruption is used in the sense of vchanlik.

According to positivism, all truly positive www. As a result of a combination of special sciences, positivism had a significant impact on the methodology of the Minister of Natural and Social Sciences, especially in the second half of the 19th century. The current form of positivism is neopositivism.

Neopositivism neo ... and positivism recognizes the face of the world as one of the main trends in 20th century philosophy. The modern form of positivism was founded by neo-positivists in the Vienna circle M. Schlick, R. Karnap, and O. Neyrat. B.Russell, L. Wittgenstein contributed to the spread of neo-positivism in England. The main ideas of neopositivism are empiricism and www. goes back to phenomenalism and neo-positivism. His ideas were reflected in the activities of the Vienna Circle, on the basis of which logical positivism was born. The science philosophy of neo-positivism was developed by Ch. Morris, P. Brijman, Upsala School in Sweden, and others.

Literature review

The following textbooks are available for this topic:

D.A.Pulatova, G.M.Ruzmatova The textbook "History of Western Philosophy" [1] The sixth section of the book is devoted to the analysis of Western philosophy in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. Emergence and directions of positivism; The philosophy of positivism in the

department, its main directions; to form a comprehensive and in-depth knowledge, understanding and understanding of the importance of the ideas of positivism in the development of science and philosophy; devoted to the formation of skills of comparative analysis of other doctrines with the philosophy of positivism.

Rustamova G, Karimova R. The textbook "History of Philosophy: Western Philosophy of the Latest Period" [2] is from 17 to 38 pages. and its main features, stages of development, the further development of positivism and its significance in the history of philosophy.

Research methodology

Western philosophy in the second half of the nineteenth century With the end of the period of Mumutoz philosophy, a new page was opened and it became the of world philosophy. It is marked by the emergence of philosophical systems that have influenced the entire philosophy of the twentieth century. The German philosopher Arthur Schopenhauer The philosophy of 1788-1860 gave rise to the notion of voluntarism. Schopenhauer sets out his main ideas in his masterpiece, *The World as Will and Imagination* (1819), which was published in 1819 as well. Although Schopenhauer's philosophical system originated in the 1920s, his work. some of his works are significant in that they remained unknown throughout his life. But at a time when the scientist's life was coming to an end, the defeat of the revolution in Germany in 1848 created the mood of economic and ideological despair of the German people. Sadness in people - an environment of regret and despair Acceptance of Schopenhauer's ideas well. There will be favorable conditions for this to happen [1].

According to John Stuart Mill (1806-1873), an English philosopher, logician and economist, the source of positivism is observation and experience. The knowledge topics given to us in the experiment are our own feelings and impressions. Mill therefore defines matter as "a constant possibility of feeling" and consciousness as a "constant possibility of experience." After Conte, Mill also divides the history of mankind into three stages from the point of view of the world, and calls them as follows [1]: -animistic (leading to personality); -existence (abstract); -phenomenological (experimental); Herbert Spencer (1820-1903) is the third representative of classical positivism. He is the founder of such works as "The Basic Principles", "Fundamentals of Biology", "Fundamentals of Sociology", "Fundamentals of Psychology", "Fundamentals of Morality", which are united in the "System of Synthetic Philosophy". classified. However, in Conte's classification, if the sciences are arranged in the order of the front and the back of the straight line according to the degree of generality, in Spencer they are abstract (logic, mathematics, and mechanics), definite ("reality-seeker"), and abstract-definite. (intermediate) [1]. Features of positivism:

- 1) emphasizes the priority of science: our knowledge is the result of scientific knowledge;
- 2) believes that scientific knowledge is based on the unity of the method, the natural scientific method, based on the definition of general laws, refers to the knowledge of society;
- 3) replaces other forms of knowledge of science;
- 4) transforms the basis of knowledge into an experience understood in a certain way, all forms of knowledge become experience;
- 5) increases the role of science and scientific progress in solving human problems.

Analysis and results

Based on the data in the studied literature, the existing concept of positivity in a person is manifested in 3 major forms.

1. Line - positivity in action
2. Emotion - innate positivity
3. Positiveness in labor activity

Let's analyze the above manifestations of positivity in a person one by one.

Emotion-is an emotional process of a person that reflects a subjectively evaluative attitude to real or abstract things. Emotions are different from influences, feelings and moods. Positiveness in birth is very important in a person, because expectancy at birth has a direct impact on other emotional processes [3].

Emotion is a moderately long-lasting emotional process that reflects a subjectively evaluative attitude to existing or possible situations. Positive emotion affects emotional positivity and stabilizes emotional continuity. aspiration, initiative, mobility. Positive feelings in preschool children are manifested in the form of stenic and asthenic feelings.

Stenic feelings - feelings can increase the vital positivity of the body (an example of stenic feelings is the appearance of feelings of joy). Asthenic feelings - on the contrary, they can reject and suppress all positivity in the body (an example of an asthenic feeling can be a feeling of sadness as opposed to joy).

Functions of human emotions that reflect positivity:

1. The stimulus function of positivity is a function that allows emotions to stimulate or reject activities aimed at satisfying needs.
2. Disorganization function of positivity - this function is manifested only in the conditions of its manifestation, and in other cases it has no functional significance.
3. The observation function of positivity - this function of emotions is manifested only in extreme conditions.
4. The heuristic function of positivity is the determination of a certain type of emotion due to the psychological mechanism at the beginning of the manifestation of emotional states.
5. The function of synthesizing positivity is to combine these emerging emotions with cognitive processes, which allows for a systematic and holistic reflection of experience and irritation.
6. The expressive function of positivity - these three functions of emotions are responsible for the communication of people in the emotional sphere.

The next manifestation of positivity is behavioral positivity, which includes all aspects of the interaction of animals and other organisms with the environment, as well as behavioral stimuli, that is, changes in the body's response to external and internal signals or combinations of signals. To understand the positivity of a behavior, it is important that we know how it occurs, how it develops in the individual, how it benefits the body, and how it arises. is passed down from generation to generation, while others are studied, that is, developed through experience. In many cases, behaviors and attitudes can have innate, or learned parts of positivity [4].

The next manifestation of positivity is positivity in labor activity. Labor is a purposeful socially useful activity of a person, first of all, changing the objects of nature and adapting them to needs. Labor is a basic condition of human life, because it creates the material and spiritual benefits necessary for human existence. Due to human activity, the objects of labor become products. Labor is the most important sign that distinguishes man from animals. He develops himself, his mental and physical abilities grow. In the process of labor, man subjugates the forces of nature to his purpose. As society develops, the division of labor emerges and deepens, new types

of labor emerge, and they become independent. Due to the specialization of labor, the mysteries of nature are studied in depth, natural objects are used to the fullest, and even their properties are changed. The level of division of labor reflects the level of productive forces in society, with the emergence of different types of labor, there is a need to exchange the results of labor activity, to adapt different activities to each other. Positiveness in work activities is manifested in the forms of positivity, such as mobility, passion, enjoyment, relaxation, when using different types of work.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, it should be noted that the problem of positivity and positivism is one of the topics studied from the distant past to the present. Positiveness in human activity is a positive state that affects the way he feels, behaves and moves.

REFERENCES

1. D. A. Po'latova, G. M. Ro'zmatova «G'arb falsafasi tarixi» o'quv qo'llanma «Fan va texnologiya» T.: 2021-yil 322-339 betlar.
2. Rustamova G. Karimova R. «Falsafa tarixi: Eng yangi davr G'arb falsafasi» o'quv qo'llanma «Universitet» T.:2017-yil 17-38 betlar.
3. B. M. Umarov «Psixologiya» darslik «Vorish-nahriyoti» T.: 2012-yil
4. M. Maxnudova «Muloqot psixologiyasi» o'quv qo'llanma «Turon-iqbol» T.: 2006-yil
5. P. I. Ivanov, M. E. Zufarova «Umumiy psixologiya» darslik «O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati» T.: 2008-yil
6. J. Hasanboyeva, X. A. To'raqulov, I. Sh. Alqarov, N. O'. Usmanov «Pedagogika» darslik «Noshir» T.: 2020-yil
7. Musurmonova «Umumiy pedagogika» o'quv qo'llanma «O'zkitobsavdonashriyoti» T.: 2020-yil
8. R. Mavlonova, O. To'rayeva, K. Xoliqberdiyev «Pedagogika» darslik «O'qituvchi» T.: 2008-yil